

Rape Myth Acceptance by Police: An Underlying Cause for Rise in Number of Unreported Cases of Sexual Assault

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Abstract

This study involves an analysis about rape myth acceptance by police as an underlying cause for unreported sexual assault cases throughout the world. Although the extent of women empowerment, gendered expectations, gender equality gap, rate of VAW and responding attitudes of survivors varies due to diverse traditional and cultural values. The aim of this research paper is to examine rape myth acceptance to the better understanding of police responses to sexual assault reports. The study also discusses various methods and techniques used by police officials of different countries while dealing and investigating sexual assault victims. The research is conducted through qualitative research methodology. Relevant data is collected by the analysis of available research work, reading materials and statistics of various countries relating to the problem. Inference as to this underlying cause has been drawn on the basis of information collected from observations and thorough study of the available literature and reports on the matter under discussion. The research would be highly significant in finding out the suitable solutions to deal with the problem with possible recommendations for policy-makers and the concerned departments for capacity building and skills development of relevant police officials and their training to investigate such issues in an appropriate way overcoming their traditional victim-blaming and patriarchal attitudes.

Background of Study

Sexual assault is common form of violence against women (VAW) globally (UN Women, 2020). It has various types including rape, sodomy, forcible object penetration, marital rape and incest. Unwanted sexual touching or coerced sexual contact is also considered to be the sexual assault. Sexual assault may be linked with other sexual crimes including sexual harassment, solicitation of minors through the internet or possession of child pornography (Marshall, 2021).

Statistics show a very dangerous scenario about the propensity of sexual assault related crimes. In the United States every 73 seconds, an American is sexually assaulted with an average of 433,648 victims per year including 82% of juvenile and 90% of adult victims as females (RAINN, 2021). 8 out of 10 rape cases involve the perpetrator knowing to the victim (NCDSV). Similar situation is found in England and Wales. An overview of sexual offending in England and Wales, the first ever bulletin on sexual violence to be released in 2013, revealed that approximately 85,000 women experience sexual assault every year (Office for National Statistics, 2013).

Like other countries of the world, sexual assault is also a major issue in Australia. Almost 2 million Australian adults have experienced at least 1 sexual assault in their lifetime since the age of 15. The rate of sexual assault recorded by the police for the year 2017 was found to be 7 times higher for females than males. In 2017-2018, 1 in 3 hospitalized sexual assault cases were identified with intimate partner as the perpetrator (AIHW, 2020).

In Pakistan, the situation is even worst with lifetime physical and/ or sexual intimate partner violence rate at 245% (UN Women, 2016). Every day at least 11 rape cases are reported with the police according to the

official statistics with around 22,000 rape cases during the last six years (The News, 2020). Almost 70 % of the Pakistani women experience physical or sexual assault in their lifetime with 93% of them who are victimized by their intimate partners (The Express Tribune, 2017).

The statistics discussed above are from few countries of the world providing the number of reported cases only. The actual number of such crimes is very high in every country which are left unreported by the survivors. Sexual assault offences are underreported due to several reasons including reluctance of survivor for being revictimized, behavior of police officials during investigation, fear of being blamed and most importantly rape myth acceptance (Richard & Seffrin, 2012).

What is Rape Myth Acceptance?

Rape myth is an idea of lying, attributed to women who delay their reporting of sexual violence, fail to recollect details of their sexual assault or feel hesitation to explain. This phrase is related to the prejudicial, stereotyped or false belief about rape, victim and rapist. Such beliefs are promoting rape cultures in societies as perpetrators are not held accountable, rather, survivors are blamed (Withers, 2019). Victim blaming is the strong element of rape myth, justifying it with the sentences like “she asked for it”; “it happens to a certain type of women”; “why she accompanied a man” or “she didn’t fight back, so it is not rape” (Crall & Goodfriend, 2016).

Rape Myth Acceptance by Police

Prompt and effective police response as well as ability and training of investigating personnel to deal with the sexual assault victims is very necessary in order to make a lead to identify and apprehend the offender. Sexual assault cases are generally categorized into two types: the one with the known offender and the other with the unknown offender, but the key issues in both the cases are the identity of the offender, the element and extent of force, and the consent (NYSCASA, 2003).

The rape victims avoid to file police reports due to the reasons of feeling guilty and embarrassed, the fear of not being believed and mistrust on the criminal justice system. Rape myth acceptance is very common among investigation officers particularly the male officials as compared to the female personnel. The extent of its acceptance is evident from the way they investigate such victims. The detectives investigating such crimes play a pivotal role in assuaging victim’s fears and uncertainties about the system (Cain, 2015).

Investigation of Rape Cases by Police Officials

According to (Dabney, 2020), detectives prefer to perform their duties basing on their professional skills, moral interests and orientation. He classified detectives of homicides into four categories including *victim-centered detectives* who struggle to provide justice to the victim and his family, the *offender-centered detectives* who try to apprehend the offender and hold him accountable, the *case-centered detectives* who take the assigned case as a puzzle and try their best to resolve that and the *hybrid detectives* who drew upon more than one of the above-mentioned types.

Research also reveals that the behavioral tactics used by male and female police officers differ when interacting with victims or public. A study about the use of behavioral tactics by male and female patrolling officials with the public revealed that male officials use coercive tactics eliciting verbal abuse from the citizens increasing the probability of physical abuse. Such behavior was not observed for female police officers (Braithwaite & Brewer, 1998).

As mentioned by (Jetmore, 2006) the rape victims do not report the incident due to their worries of unsympathetic treatment from police and discomforting procedure, lack of belief in the ability of police to arrest the suspect, fear of further victimization by court proceedings and news reports, embarrassment and fear of reprisal by the rapist.

Police Perception about Rape Victims

It has been observed by (Jordan, 2004) that police responses to sexual assault complaints are shaped by rape myth acceptance among officials. In such matters women are stereotypically judged by the police and their credibility is questioned, which impacts police decision to proceed with an investigation negatively. In another study (Jordan, 2001) discussed how women's rape complainants are treated by the police and the criminal justice system that affects the rate of reporting the crimes.

Despite of high rate of underreporting, there remains a perception among the general public (as believed by 2 of 5 Australians) that women lie or exaggerate the report to get advantage in their relationship with men (ANROWS, 2018). Police officers also believe that women frequently make false allegations of sexual assault (Venema, 2018). Studies of (Wager, 2019) reveal that the previous allegations about sexual assault victimization affect the credibility of the complainant, particularly with the history of childhood sexual assault, attributing victim-blame.

Sexual assault victims have to face more scrutiny than other crime victims due to the misconception of false reporting and lying on the part of the victim. They have to face strong interrogation by the law enforcement during the process of gathering information from them in order to establish credibility and to assess whether an assault indeed occurred. They have to undergo the process of interrogation with the expectation of revealing all the facts to reach the truth (Davis, 2013). This whole process results into how a victim is constructed by the personnel. Consequently, it affects the case processing, decision making and apprehension of perpetrator (Dewald & Lorenz, 2021).

The perception of false reporting among investigators cannot be generalized. Not believing in victims may impart detrimental results (Dewald & Lorenz, 2021). The victims are reluctant to report the crimes due to the aggressive treatment by the police officials. They avoid reporting to avoid re-traumatization often caused by invasive questions of the investigating officer (Davis, 2013). Studies reveal that male police officers are more likely than female officers to believe that reported sexual assault allegations are false (Sleath & Bull, 2017).

It was concluded by (Page, 2008) that, although the police officers take the crime of rape seriously, they often discredit victims. This can affect the confidence of women victims to come forward to disclose what happened to them. A study was conducted by (O'Neal, 2017) of officer perceptions of complainant of "character flaws" basing on various indicators including presence of reputation issue, complainant suffering from any mental issue, inconsistency of her testimony or any motive to lie.

It was found that such perceptions as to 'character flaws' negatively affect the credibility of the victim in the perception of the officer. Lack of proper sensitization in dealing with sexual assault victims generate many behavioral and attitudinal problems by the investigators against the survivors resulting into biased investigation and false-blaming (Imran, Sajid, Naushad, & Khan, 2010).

As identified by (Franklin, Garza, Goodson, & Bouffard, 2019) police perceptions of a victim's self-presentation style including their flat or restricted affect, emotional disorienting and split recollection can leave an impact on secondary victimization, case processing and public safety.

The study (Kamal, Shaikh, & Shaikh, 2010) discussed the gendered based attitudes and beliefs blaming the female rape victims and found it commonly present among men than women. Findings of the study by (Nisar, et al., 2021) suggested that people who misinterpret traditional gender roles are more likely to adhere with rape myths and develop negative opinions about the rape and the rapist. The study recommended that this negative attitude and belief about the rape victims, gender roles and sexuality can be eliminated through education and rape prevention programs.

Police officials themselves are found involved in several sexual assault cases. Such incidents adversely affect the credibility of the whole police department resultantly the victims are reluctant to approach them for reporting and assistance seeking (Ijaz, Rape allegations against Pakistan's police, 2019).

Women chanted on the streets of major cities across Pakistan protesting against the police official's response to "motorway case" involving the rape of a woman by two men in front of her three children who was driving on Lahore-Sialkot motorway after midnight and had to stop as her car ran out of fuel and she was waiting for her relative as the police refused to respond because the location was out of their jurisdiction (Ijaz, Blaming the victim for sexual violence in Pakistan, 2020). The victim-blaming statement of the serving CCPO Lahore, as to why she travelled with her children so late at night, shattered the public trust in police reflecting masculinity and patriarchal mindset (Pasha, 2020).

Motorway case became a high-profile case due to the media attention, inviting the prompt response from the law enforcement and criminal justice system. If the incident had occurred in some rural or backward area or against a woman with low social background, it would have never been decided in such a manner or left unreported or dismissed at the very initial stage or inaccurately recorded. It has been observed that the woman's class and her residence are the primary factors to attract police official's response to their complaint (Pasha, Gendered response to policing in Pakistan, 2020).

Consequences of Rape Myth Acceptance by Police

Rape myth acceptance leaves adverse effects on the victim, the rapist as well as the society. Its acceptance by police and the prevailing image of the police officials results into reluctance of the victims in reporting crime. It is not only increasing the number of unreported sexual assault cases but also encouraging the perpetrators to commit further crimes. In this way the rape is being reinforced.

Rape myth acceptance not only affects the number of reported cases but also results into low conviction rate. In United States 3 out of 4 sexual assault cases go unreported whereas the conviction rate in reported cases is just 4.6% (RAINN). In England and Wales also the number of reported cases is much lesser with conviction rate in reported cases at 5.7% (The National Archive, 2013). In Australia, the number of female sexual assault victim seeking police advice or support is only 1 in 6. Almost 87% of the female victims during the last 10 years did not contact police according to PSS estimation (AIHW, 2020).

As disclosed by Madadgaar Helpline representative in a press conference, in Pakistan only 10% of the sexual assault cases are reported with almost 90% of those which are unreported (The Express Tribune, 2017). The conviction rate in sexual assault cases in Pakistan is abysmally low i.e. around 3% (Global Village Space, 2020). From June 2013 to February 2015, only 219 out of 6,632 arrested persons in 4,960 rape cases were convicted in Pakistan (The Asia Foundation, 2015).

The police perception about the victims often leads to false acquittal or false conviction. It increases the sense of insecurity among the citizens particularly the females who are more vulnerable and are likely to be victimized and re-victimized. Responsibility of police is to investigate the matter and apprehend the offender and not to make self-assumptions and deciding the case on the basis of perceptions only holding the victim responsible for the incident.

Freedom of movement and protection against person and property are the fundamental rights of every person. It is the responsibility of every state to provide protection to its citizens. Law provides equal protection to all the citizens without any discrimination on the basis of sex. Provision of justice, fair trial and opportunity to hearing are also the rights of the individuals who are victimized in any form. The persons who fail to get justice lose their trust in state and the relevant institutions. It also destroys the international image of the state portraying an environment without law-and-order situation raising questions on security standards of the country.

It is the duty of the police to safeguard the citizens, taking prompt action when any offence is committed, investigating the matter without any bias and partiality and arresting the offender for trial. But the behavior of police in sexual assault cases does not reflect any professional attitude. It amounts to further harass the women instead of providing them justice resultantly shattering the trust of the victims instead all the vulnerable in the law enforcement.

The victim-blaming by the police, media and the courts affects the reputation of the victims who lose their confidence to face the society. Due to re-victimization and social stigmatization, the victims do not come out their post-traumatic condition and suffer from severe mental health issues. Often, they commit suicide or suicidal attempts. They also have to face reprisal sometimes by the rapist. Feelings of threat, shock and fear do not mitigate.

Conclusion

Detailed study of the available information revealed that the rape myth acceptance is a universal dilemma both at societal as well as institutional level. Its acceptance by the police is leaving the victims unsupported with her grievance unredressed and the reputation damaged alongwith social stigmatization and emotional as well as psychological traumas. This is all due to the patriarchal mindset of the society particularly of the sexual assault cases investigators who play a pivotal role in resolving such matters. This perception needs to be radically changed so that the women could feel the sense of protection and further incidents could be controlled by punishing the perpetrators. The institutional reforms are also required with respect to the capacity building of the police officials and their resourcefulness in addition to their trainings for skills enhancement. Keeping in view this study and its findings, the following recommendations are being proffered in this regard:

Recommendations

1. The theory of *police omnipresence* that the police are everywhere, and if anybody commits a crime, he will be rapidly apprehended, must be applied. It is a fact that almost 80 percent of the forcible rapes cannot be prevented for being occurred indoor, featuring some intimacy between the victim and the offender. Prompt response of police officials to the crime scene after receiving the call may help in securing and collecting the valuable evidence against the perpetrator.
2. After reaching the scene, the first duty of the responders must be to treat the victim in a compassionate manner so that she could be able to answer their questions without feeling herself blamed and ashamed. The investigation and interviews by the members of investigating team must be conducted in a setting most comfortable to the victim.
3. Conviction in such matters requires corroboration through physical and circumstantial evidence in addition to the victim's testimony in the court. Therefore, the proper collection, documentation, preservation and careful analysis of physical evidence is very crucial to reach the actual offender and to exonerate if someone is falsely accused. It is possible only if the concerned officials are trained enough for the purpose of securing and searching the scene as well as identifying and handling the valuable evidence.
4. It is important to gain trust of the victim ensuring them that you are there to help them and require them to be honest about the incident for thorough investigation. Reassure them that their privacy would be respected at all times and nothing would be discussed with their family, friends, co-workers, employer or spouse. The investigation must be victim-centered facilitating them even about the time and place to meet them.
5. The investigating officer must listen the victim with an open mind by believing them. He should neither be biased in his opinion nor he should respond in a judgmental or demeaning way. The victim must be provided proper psychological counselling to control their feelings of fear, trauma, self-blame, shame or embarrassment so that they could recollect the experience and could be able to explain.
6. Repeated investigations mostly aggravate the trauma and affects the mental health of the victim resultantly the victim prefers to withdraw the complaint and steps back. Investigation in such cases must be concluded efficaciously without letting the victim to face the concerned personnel one by one at various times and later on answering the questions of the counsels during court proceedings disclosing the same facts publicly with impeachment of their own credit and facing injuries to their credit with the blame of being a prosecutrix. Such practice affects their mental health adversely putting them in a state of continuous revictimization by recalling the same incident. Such practice must be discouraged and the whole proceeding must be conducted keeping in view the standards of

decency without dealing the victim as a crime partner or blaming them for whatever happened to them was their own fault.

7. Presumption of innocence is always attached with the accused and he is not declared guilty unless the accusation is proved beyond reasonable doubt. In such cases the matter is strange as the accused is still considered to be the innocent but the victim is dealt as an offender in an insulting manner without believing them by taking her allegation or grievance as a myth with a presumption that '*she asked for it*'. This practice must be discouraged and the victim must be treated with due respect leaving the case to be decided on the basis of facts and evidence instead of false and self-made assumptions of the officials.
8. The government must introduce necessary measures regarding ensuring privacy during investigation and trial of such offences without publicizing the victim. It may encourage the victims to report their cases.
9. The offenders must be declared and punished publicly so that the continuous rise in the ratio of such offences could be controlled. The publicity and punishment of the offender would put the others with similar instinct into fear of injury to their reputation helping in preventing such crimes in future.
10. Women protection units and centers should be established for providing suitable assistance, psychological support and guidance to the victims to help them to overcome post traumatic situations and securing them from revictimization due to getting involved in drug abuse, alcohol abuse or attending parties to relieve stress and forget the incident. Proper counselling only can help them to overcome their situation.
11. Female police officers must be recruited and deployed for these offences so that the survivors of sexual assault may get the assistance they need.
12. Wages, working hours and working environment should be improved so that the officials may perform their duties with interest and dedication. They should be rewarded for their good job and must be punished for any negligence.
13. Workshops and seminars should be arranged with the joint efforts of police, media, Women Protection Centers and concerned NGO's. The objective of such activities should be to make women feel protected by clearing the image of police.

Bibliography

- AIHW. (2020, August). *Sexual assault in Australia*. Retrieved from www.aihw.gov.au:https://www.aihw.gov.au/getmedia/0375553f-0395-46cc-9574-d54c74fa601a/aihw-fdv-5.pdf.aspx?inline=true
- AIHW. (2020, August 28). *Sexual Assault in Australia*. Retrieved from www.aihw.gov.au:https://www.aihw.gov.au/reports/domestic-violence/sexual-assault-in-australia/contents/summary
- ANROWS. (2018). *Australians' attitude to violence against women and gender equality. Finding from the 2017 National Community Attitude towards Violence against Women Survey (NCAS)*. Retrieved from [www.anrows.org.au: https://www.anrows.org.au/NCAS/2017/4-attitudes-to-violence-against-women/](http://www.anrows.org.au:https://www.anrows.org.au/NCAS/2017/4-attitudes-to-violence-against-women/)
- Braithwaite, H., & Brewer, N. (1998). Differences in the conflict resolution tactics of male and female police patrol officers. *International Journal of Police Science Management*, 276.
- Cain, N. (2015, Apr 27). *Interview strategies for sexual assault and rape investigations*. Retrieved from [www.police1.com: https://www.police1.com/police-products/interview-recording/articles/interview-strategies-for-sexual-assault-and-rape-investigations-JFKGngjHdNnshZUw/](http://www.police1.com:https://www.police1.com/police-products/interview-recording/articles/interview-strategies-for-sexual-assault-and-rape-investigations-JFKGngjHdNnshZUw/)
- Crall, P., & Goodfriend, W. (2016). She asked for it: Statistics and predictors of rape myth acceptance. *Modern Psychological Studies*.
- Dabney, D. (2020). Doing death work: a typology of how homicide detectives orient to their work. *Policing and Society*, 777-794.
- Davis, S. M. (2013, May). Sexual assault detectives' justifications for aggressive interviewing methods: A qualitative study. *Dissertation*. Las Vegas.
- Dewald, S., & Lorenz, K. (2021). Lying about sexual assault: a qualitative study of detective perspective on false reporting. *Policing and Society*.

- Franklin, C. A., Garza, A. D., Goodson, A., & Bouffard, L. A. (2019). Police perceptions of crime victim behaviors: A trend analysis exploring mandatory training and knowledge of sexual and domestic violence survivor's trauma response. *Crime & Delinquency*.
- Global Village Space. (2020, September 15). *Conviction rate in rape cases under 3% in Pakistan: Report*. Retrieved from www.globalvillagespace.com: <https://www.globalvillagespace.com/conviction-rate-in-rape-cases-under-3-in-pakistan-report/>
- Ijaz, S. (2019, May 23). *Rape allegations against Pakistan's police*. Retrieved from www.hrw.org: <https://www.hrw.org/news/2019/05/23/rape-allegations-against-pakistans-police>
- Ijaz, S. (2020, September 14). *Blaming the victim for sexual violence in Pakistan*. Retrieved from www.hrw.org: <https://www.hrw.org/news/2020/09/14/blaming-victim-sexual-violence-pakistan>
- Imran, A., Sajid, I. A., Naushad, A., & Khan, S. (2010). Violence against women in Pakistan: Constraints in investigation and data collection. *Journal of Criminology*.
- Jamshed, N., & Kamal, A. (2019). Prevalence of rape myths and sexual double standards among university students in Pakistan. *Journal of Interpersonal Violence*.
- Jetmore, D. L. (2006, Jun 15). *Investigating Rape Crimes, Part1: Guidelines for first responders*. Retrieved from www.police1.com: <https://www.police1.com/police-products/investigation/evidence-management/articles/investigating-rape-crimes-part-1-guidelines-for-first-responders-Szghj3goS1WxaXUu/>
- Jordan, J. (2004). Beyond Belief?: Police, Rape and Women's Credibility. *Criminology & Criminal Justice*.
- Kamal, A., Shaikh, I. A., & Shaikh, M. A. (2010). Comparative analysis of attitude and perceptions about rape among male and female university students. *Journal of Ayub Medical College Abbotabad*, 108-110.
- Marshall. (2021). *Types of sexual assault*. Retrieved from www.marshall.edu: <https://www.marshall.edu/wcenter/sexual-assault/types-of-sexual-assault/>
- Marshall. (n.d.). *Types of Sexual Assault*. Retrieved from www.marshall.edu: <https://www.marshall.edu/wcenter/sexual-assault/types-of-sexual-assault/>
- NCDSV. (n.d.). *Sexual Assault Statistics*. Retrieved from www.ncdsv.org: <http://www.ncdsv.org/images/sexualassaultstatistics.pdf>
- NHMRC. (2018). *National statement on ethical conduct in human research*. Retrieved from www.nhmrc.gov.au: <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/about-us/publications/national-statement-ethical-conduct-human-research-2007-updated-2018>
- Nisar, S., Zafar, K., Batool, D. I., Ishfaq, M., Fatima, H., Fatima, K., & Arshad, R. (2021). Ambivalent sexism towards women and acceptance of rape myths among university students. *Saudi Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 90-95.
- NYSCASA. (2003). *Pocket Guide for Police response to Sexual Assault*. New York: New York State Coalition Against Sexual Assault.
- Office for National Statistics. (2013, January 10). *An overview of sexual offending in England & Wales, Joint Publication*. Retrieved from www.webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk: <https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20160106113426/http://www.ons.gov.uk/ons/rel/crime-stats/an-overview-of-sexual-offending-in-england---wales/december-2012/index.html>
- O'Neal, E. N. (2017). Victim is not credible: The influence of rape culture on police perceptions of sexual assault complainants. *Justice Quarterly*.
- Page, A. D. (2008). Judging women and defining crime: Police officers' attitudes towards women and rape. *Social Spectrum*.
- Pasha, A. (2020, September 28). *Gendered response to policing in Pakistan*. Retrieved from www.thenews.com.pk: <https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/721093-gendered-response-to-policing-in-pakistan>
- Petrak, J., Doyle, A.-M., Buchan, L., & Forster, G. (1997). The psychological impact of sexual assault: A study of female attenders of a sexual health psychology service. *Sexual and Marital Therapy*, 12:339-45.
- RAINN. (2021). *Victims of sexual violence: Statistics*. Retrieved from www.rainn.org: <https://www.rainn.org/statistics/victims-sexual-violence>

- RAINN. (n.d.). *The Criminal Justice System*. Retrieved from [www.rainn.org: https://www.rainn.org/statistics/criminal-justice-system](http://www.rainn.org/statistics/criminal-justice-system)
- RAINN. (n.d.). *Victims of sexual violence: Statistics*. Retrieved from [www.rainn.org: https://www.rainn.org/statistics/victims-sexual-violence](http://www.rainn.org/statistics/victims-sexual-violence)
- Richard, K., & Seffrin, P. (2012). Police interviews of sexual assault reporters: Do attitude matter? *Violence and Victims*.
- Sleath, E., & Bull, R. (2017). Police perception of rape victims and the impact on case decision making: A systematic review. *Aggression and violent behaviour*, 102-112.
- The Asia Foundation. (2015, November 11). *Compromising Justice: Pakistan's low conviction rates for rape*. Retrieved from [www.asiafoundation.org: https://asiafoundation.org/2015/11/11/compromising-justice-pakistans-low-conviction-rates-for-rape/](http://www.asiafoundation.org)
- The Express Tribune. (2017, March 08). *93% of Pakistani women experience Sexual Violence*. Retrieved from [www.tribune.com.pk: https://tribune.com.pk/story/1348833/93-pakistani-women-experience-sexual-violence](http://www.tribune.com.pk)
- The National Archive. (2013, January 10). *An overview of Sexual Offending in England and Wales*. Retrieved from [www.webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk: https://webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk/20160106113426/http://www.ons.gov.uk/ons/rel/crime-stats/an-overview-of-sexual-offending-in-england---wales/december-2012/index.html](http://www.webarchive.nationalarchives.gov.uk)
- The News. (2020, November 13). *11 rape incidents reported in Pakistan every day, official statistics reveal*. Retrieved from [www.thenews.com.pk: https://www.thenews.com.pk/latest/743328-about-11-rape-cases-reported-in-pakistan-every-day-official-statistics-reveal#:~:text=There%20are%20at%20least%2011,0.3%25%20of%20the%20total%20figure.](http://www.thenews.com.pk)
- UN Women. (2016). *Global database on Violence against women*. Retrieved from [www.evaw-global-database.unwomen.org: https://evaw-global-database.unwomen.org/es/countries/asia/pakistan?formofviolence=c6ff23e9fc6e4f0aa974d0da1611b98f#1](http://www.evaw-global-database.unwomen.org)
- UN Women. (2020, November). *Facts and Figures: Ending violence against women*. Retrieved from [www.women.org: https://www.unwomen.org/en/what-we-do/ending-violence-against-women/facts-and-figures](http://www.women.org)
- Venema, R. M. (2018). Police officer's rape myth acceptance: Examining the role of officer characteristics, estimates of false reporting, and social desirability bias. *Violence and Victims*.
- Wager, N. M. (2019). An experimental investigation of the perceived credibility of complainant of sexual revictimization: Disbelief and victim-blame. *Violence and Victims*.
- Weiss, K. G. (2010). Too ashamed to report: Deconstructing the shame of sexual victimization. *Sage Journals*.
- WHO. (2001, January). *Putting women first: Ethical and safety recommendations for research on domestic violence against women*. Retrieved from [www.who.int: https://www.who.int/gender-equity-rights/knowledge/who_fch_gwh_01.1/en/](http://www.who.int)
- Withers, M. (2019, August 06). *Rape Myth Acceptance Leading to Victim-Blaming*. Retrieved from [www.psychologytoday.com: https://www.psychologytoday.com/us/blog/modern-day-slavery/201908/rape-myth-acceptance-leads-victim-blaming](http://www.psychologytoday.com)
- Women, U. (2020, November). *Facts and Figures: Ending violence against women*. Retrieved from [www.unwomen.org: https://www.unwomen.org/en/what-we-do/ending-violence-against-women/facts-and-figures](http://www.unwomen.org)

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